

Sociological Analysis of Novel Manglua: War Between Villages, Elope, Irony of Batak Custom By Mulia Nasution

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is to find out the value of sociology in the Manglua novel. The study of sociology in this novel covers the social aspect of society which is objective and related to people's attitudes. This research is interrelated with social relations and people's lives. Therefore, the structure relates to the origin of the work.

Keywords: *Novel Manglua, Adat Batak Toba, Perang Antar kampung, Kawin Lari*

INTRODUCTION

In this Manglua novel, readers can understand that in the Batak Toba community, the Manglua custom is still a habit. Both customs and religions such as Catholicism, Protestantism, as well as Batak ancestral customs, still carry it out. Therefore, Manglua's novel is very interesting to be analyzed and discussed. This Manglua tradition occurs as a result of a dowry (sinamot) because the groom's family cannot afford it, there is no compatibility, because there are still conflicts between villages.

Generally, this Mangluan custom is detrimental to the woman's family. His family will be looked down upon and can hurt the honor of a family. The Manglua tradition often occurs in the speech of the fathers of the indigenous peoples of Lampung, Batak, Bali, Bugis/Makassar, Mandailing, Angkola, Lombok, and Maluku. This means that this tradition problem can be understood as an effort to resolve the problem of conflict from various parties, especially from the women's side.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. This novel is very suitable for analysis. Because this novel explains

in detail social, economic, and religious values. Besides that, this novel is easy to analyze, because its content is very complete. includes several elements, such as the structure of the story, themes, characteristics, and the setting of the story in the Manglua novel.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions is manglua novel-themed about sublime peace. This novel tells the story of the main role figure, namely jogal who strives for humans because of the war between villages. This creates misery for society. Jogal runs away and proceeds to apologize and pay the fine. This is rejection. However, in the end, there was a customary marriage between the two families. The bride's party is a child named Si Boru Anting, a gentle noble daughter.

In terms of sociological analysis, this novel discusses the kidnapping of Si Boru Anting. Since being appointed as Sisimangaraja XII, there is not much resistance between villages against the Dutch. However, Si Boru Earring was kidnapped and taken to Huta Bariba. The Dutch entered houses and asked for negotiations with the people they met. After that, the KNIL war broke out and about 70% of the people of Huta Porlak were baptized. According to some sources, the resistance between villages occurred because they adhered to old beliefs, expanded their territory, and showed strength.

CONCLUSION

How the writer subjectively sees from the paper analysis that This novel tells about the Mangluan tradition, not only that Batak culture is also told in this novel, such as events and the names of all characters with Batak elements. The Manglua novel contains cultural values, local wisdom, open confessions of love, and also political battles between the villages in it. In addition, this analysis explains a lot about the resistance between villages that aims to seize territory and show strength between the two parties

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